

THE NECESSITY OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Kurbanbaeva Mirigul Jenisbaevna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the process of reforming foreign language teaching has intensified due to the globalization of social, economic and political problems around the world. Teaching and learning foreign languages are becoming a vital necessity for every nation. In modern Uzbekistan, the role of teaching and developing foreign languages, especially English, is currently of great value. Learning English is a necessity of life and represents one of the basic requirements of modern society.

INTRODUCTION

Today, learning and mastering a foreign language is of particular importance. In connection with modern requirements and scientific and technological progress, we are increasingly faced with the fact that knowledge of language is necessary and is an integral factor for success in a multicultural world. The study of foreign languages provides for the development of international cooperation, open access to the achievements of world science and information resources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Continuity in learning is the opportunity to acquire knowledge and professional skills, abilities that gradually develop throughout life, which ensures constant replenishment and expansion of knowledge. This program is considered effective and is aimed at creating the necessary conditions for the formation of creative, socially active and spiritually rich personnel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article discusses the issue of learning English in the system of continuing education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The author analyzed the issues of continuity in teaching a foreign language as an effective criterion for a system of non-stop improvement in the level of education. As many methodological researchers note, one of the main criteria in teaching English is the creation of a foreign language environment that ensures communication. Our observations and analysis of the literature showed that to achieve this goal it is necessary that students study English throughout their lives (Lifelong learning), i.e. continuously. This concept is most clearly formulated in the work of Voitovich, who in his monograph "Foreign languages in the context of lifelong education" notes: "The creation of a system of lifelong foreign language education is no less interesting and exciting process, because lifelong foreign language

education is a large integrated field that goes far beyond the boundaries of pedagogy or linguistics" [4, p.196].

The theory of lifelong education in English language learning has also been considered by specialists who argue that lifelong education "is formed as a methodological synthesis of student-oriented pedagogical concepts, on the one hand, and the concepts of "human capital" and "economic knowledge" on the other" [2, 11]. V. Arnautov, noting the importance of continuous language education, noted four goals of this concept: dissemination of culture, preparation of citizens for the changing conditions of social development, additional education for all, advanced training at all levels of the education system [3].

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The main principles of creating and developing continuity are priority, democratization, humanization, humanitarization, national orientation, continuity of education and upbringing and identification of gifted youth. These principles were applied and were taken as a basis in the formation of new textbooks and state educational standards in relation to teaching foreign languages. Consequently, foreign language teaching at all levels of continuing education is systematized and predetermined.

In our domestic education, this term is used to refer to the country's state policy and the system of non-stop raising the level of education. This provides each person with the necessary knowledge, professional skills and specialties throughout his life. At the international conference "Preparation of an educated and intellectually developed generation - as the most important condition for sustainable development and modernization of the country," noting the importance of the principle of continuity in language teaching, prof. Seoul Polytechnic College Ban Hwan said that the system of continuous education in the languages of Uzbekistan has received recognition in the world community and implements the principle of advanced systems - lifelong education [2]. The need for lifelong education was discussed as part of a Round Table in 2015 at a meeting of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on the topic "Priority tasks for the development of a National Strategy for further strengthening continuous and high-quality non-formal education in Uzbekistan, which emphasized that lifelong learners are better prepared to adapt to changes in your life. Consequently, this ensures the solution of strategic tasks set for society. The need to transform non-institutionalized organizations, which provide the opportunity to study at any time, anywhere, in any conditions, was also noted.

Within the framework of this article, we have analyzed some stages of training separately, considering the levels of English language training within the framework of the corresponding state educational standard:

- Preschool education. This stage is considered the most important in teaching English, since during this period children develop the skills and abilities to speak both their native and foreign languages. In light of the implementation of Decree PP No. 1875, fruitful work on learning through play will be introduced in preschool educational institutions, i.e. this is memorizing new words and phrases, learning poems and songs by heart, and more.

All this implies that at this stage the role in teaching speaking is considered partially.

- General secondary education. This stage is divided into primary and senior education. At the initial stage, students learn English in a playful way, and must have a level on the CEFR scale (Adapted system for assessing the level of language proficiency) - A1. High school graduates must have a B1+ level, which is equal to the level of independent advanced proficiency in a foreign language. At this stage, students actively learn communication skills of speaking, reading, writing and listening.

- Secondary specialized vocational education. This stage of training also involves learning the language through authentic materials aimed at mastering communicative competence. The level of language proficiency is equal to graduates of general secondary education.

It should also be noted that general secondary and secondary specialized vocational education are mandatory, which in turn is confirmed by law

"About Education". This will undoubtedly enable our youth to master the basic knowledge and skills to achieve their goals in learning English.

- Higher education. At this stage, graduates must master levels from B2-C1 upon completion of training, based on the linguistic or non-linguistic profile of education. Based on the above levels, students study English in their specialty, which provides them with the necessary knowledge and skills of communicative competence.

CONCLUSION

Within the framework of our article, consideration of non-institutionalized training was not provided, but in general, the study of English at these stages is also fruitfully mastered.

Thus, as noted above, continuous study of English involves the preparation of highly qualified, competitive personnel at all stages of training.

The goal is to prepare a mentally and physically developed future generation that is fluent in English and can function in a multicultural world in all areas. In conclusion, I would like to note that the role and importance of teaching English in continuity and continuity is positive, which is the main criterion for effective teaching of a foreign language.

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